

Heterogeneous landscape of environmental indicators and other metrics used in the science-policy arena

Yanina V. Sica*[^] [ORCID:0000-0002-1720-0127], Renske M. Gudde* (ORCID:0000-0003-4727-1011), Manuela Gomez-Suarez*[^] [ORCID:0000-0002-6100-9207], Lina M. Estupinan-Suarez⁺ [ORCID: 0000-0002-2359-9496], Shawn Dove[^] [ORCID: 0000-0001-9465-5638], Jessica Hetzer* [ORCID: 0000-0002-2384-0024], Hanno Seebens[^], Aidin Niamir* [ORCID: 0000-0003-4511-3407]

*Senckenberg Biodiversity and Climate Research Institute, Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung, Frankfurt am Main, Germany

[^]Ecological Informatics, Department of Animal Ecology & Systematics, Justus Liebig University, Gießen, Germany.

⁺German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig.

Abstract (should be 250)

Indicators and other metrics used to assess social and ecological systems are vital for monitoring environmental status and evaluating policy effectiveness. However, identifying suitable indicators is challenging due to the variety of metrics available and the lack of a centralised resource to find them. To address this, we reviewed the strategic plans of 10 biodiversity-focused Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEA) and three major global environmental assessments carried out by science-policy organisations, and systematically searched for metrics. We harmonised and classified these metrics according to the specific elements they measure.

We retrieved a total of 1,829 unique metrics: 657 from MEAs and 1,356 from assessments, encompassing all elements of the socio-ecological system, with a majority focused on Ecosystems (28.3%), Governance (14.2%), and Direct Drivers (12.1%). Only 11.4% of all metrics are reused among MEAs and assessments, indicating that MEAs monitor progress towards their targets in distinct ways. The exception is the Global Biodiversity Framework, which uses 15.8% of the indicators proposed in other MEAs and 32.8% from science-policy assessments.

This heterogeneous indicator landscape reflects the multifaceted aspects of socio-ecological systems; science-policy assessments bring a more integrated approach by considering bundles of

metrics that measure the whole environment, whereas MEAs are more constrained. The lack of consistency in naming and conceptualisation of metrics and indicators hampers their reuse in policy-making and increases the burden of countries' commitments. Collaborative efforts between science and policy are essential for monitoring global progress toward environmental targets.

Keywords

biodiversity monitoring, environmental policy effectiveness, global treaties, assessment reports, MEAs

Introduction

Environmental indicators and other quantitative metrics are crucial to understand societal relationships with nature, assess the state of nature, and track changes (e.g., Pereira et al. 2013, Tittensor et al. 2014, Geijzenborffer et al. 2016). In the policy arena, indicators are key tools for monitoring progress towards goals such as those formulated in Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs). In this context, a fair and consistent comparison of progress across countries can only be achieved with indicators that are not only sensitive to changes in the system but also simple (easy to measure consistently), scalable, and evidence-based (Heink & Kowarik, 2010; Rapport & Hildén, 2013).

A key lesson learnt from the failure to meet the Aichi Biodiversity Targets (Butchart et al., 2010; Walpole et al., 2009) is the need for frameworks which explicitly detail the mechanisms to quantify the progress of MEAs (Hughes et al., 2022; Mcowen et al., 2016). An attempt was made in the monitoring framework of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KM-GBF), where signatory countries have agreed on a set of quantitative and qualitative indicators for each of its goals and targets (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2025). While a significant step, the success of the monitoring framework of KM-GBF requires not only robust indicators, but also political commitment and cooperation at all levels of government, research, and society: signatory countries are required to develop technical capacities to report the numerous indicators, posing a big burden, particularly on developing economies (Haugen et al., 2024), and scientists need to better reflect societal well-being in their proposed quantitative measurements (Rees et al., 2008). This challenge provides an opportunity for countries and indicator experts (researchers, data managers, and decision-makers) to work more closely together to agree upon what parameters to measure, how to measure them, and what data to use in a fit-for-purpose

way (Jones et al., 2011). Such a collaborative, openly available, global monitoring system is needed to face the current triple crisis of biodiversity, climate, and pollution, while some frameworks have been proposed (Gonzalez et al., 2023, 2025), the urgency is paramount.

Intergovernmental science–policy platforms provide the means for such collaborative work as they were established to improve communication between science and policy. Their goal is to provide the best evidence on the status and trends of nature and people in an actionable way for the whole of society to use. These interfaces integrate scientific, Indigenous and local knowledge to support decision-making. They generally do so by developing assessments where they inform policy-makers not only about the status of the world, but also about the methods to measure and monitor the environment and its changes. For example, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) has recruited experts who are assessing methods to monitor biodiversity, nature’s contributions to people, the direct and underlying causes of change, and progress towards the goals and targets of the KM-GBF and other MEAs to support national strategies. This assessment is expected to be finalised in 2027. Standardised indicators and metrics are at the heart of such assessments since they provide a common thread and a point of comparison among assessments, facilitating the synthesis work (IPBES, 2018).

During the last couple of decades, we have witnessed a boom in environmental indicators worldwide (Birk et al., 2012; Canedoli et al., 2024; Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013; Teixeira et al., 2016). This has been driven by the development of specific policy requirements (*i.e.*, monitoring frameworks) and by research attempting to cover different aspects of the multifaceted socio-ecological system. For example, scientists have been developing measurements for species habitats (Kumagai et al., 2022), endangered taxa (Gatti et al., 2015), threats to ecosystems (Halpern et al., 2012), and their services (Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013b), among others. However, many of these measures remain in the scientific literature and are not used by policymakers and governmental agencies (Bhatt et al., 2020). Conversely, several indicators proposed in MEAs are rarely assessed in scientific studies or lack technical development.

Reasons for the inconsistent use of indicators are manifold; one identified obstacle to the adoption and use of existing indicators is the tedious and time-consuming task of searching for potential metrics already available (Teixeira et al., 2016). The lack of harmonisation and documentation of metrics has been a limitation to the reusability of such metrics, on top of the lack of available data globally. There is no common framework on how to develop, use or document metrics; hence, the reusability of metrics when available is low. The Biodiversity Indicator Partnership (<https://www.bipindicators.net/>) provided guidelines and made a great effort in collating biodiversity indicators, but this initiative was not continued. The multiplicity

and variety of new indicators developed or proposed make such efforts easily outdated. Thus, optimising the findability and accessibility of indicators is critical for policymakers to apply indicators in assessments and regulatory contexts (Queirós et al., 2016; Rees et al., 2008). However, it remains unclear how indicators are used across MEAs and assessments, and which aspects of the socio-ecological system are covered the most.

Here, we present a comprehensive review of the indicators and other metrics (see definitions below) used in key ongoing biodiversity-focused MEAs and assessments carried out by major science-policy organisations. We gathered and harmonised indicators from these MEAs and assessments and compared their use within and across the policy and scientific realms. We were particularly interested in evaluating the diversity of metrics proposed, their reusability across realms, and identifying gaps in the coverage of the socio-ecological system. The aggregated list of metrics that measure multiple elements of the social-ecological system is provided, including information on the elements they describe and the framework in which they were included.

Methods

What is an indicator?

Quantitative metrics play a key role in establishing a common language and facilitating comparisons across measurements (IPBES, 2018). In this context, a metric can be an indicator, index, or variable that is used to measure some aspect of the socio-ecological system. These concepts are often confused or used as synonyms. In the scientific literature, indicators are often used in their broadest sense, being measurements used to monitor the status and trend of an object or process (Belcher et al., 2024; Heink & Kowarik, 2010). In a policy context, indicators are used to track progress towards agreed goals and targets, and may be a proxy for something different from what they measure, conveying information about more than themselves (Brooks & Bubb, 2014; Rees et al., 2008). The Essential Biodiversity Variables framework was developed to join both scientific and policy views. Following the Essential Climatic Variables (GCOS, 2010), the framework aims to standardise the key variables or descriptors of the environment (*i.e.*, metrics) needed to calculate policy-relevant indicators related to biodiversity (Jetz et al., 2019; Pereira et al., 2013). In this work, we are following this framework, referring to **metrics** as any form of standardised data, information, and knowledge that describes or measures the status, trends, or outcomes of specific objects or processes (IPBES, 2019), including indicators, indices, and variables. We use the term **indicators** as any metric applied towards a policy need, and we distinguish them from **indices** as an aggregation of indicators into a single representation.

Search and review process

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the different metrics used in the science-policy arena, we searched for these metrics in global, ongoing Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs) focused on biodiversity and nature, as well as global assessment reports carried out by major international organisations working at the interface of policy and science. We identified three international organisations which regularly release relevant assessments:

- The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) is the United Nations' body to assess nature and people. It brings together governments, scientists, and various stakeholders to assess biodiversity's status and trends worldwide. The IPBES assessments published from 2019 to 2024 were reviewed for this work: i) the Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services (IPBES, 2019), ii) the Methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature (IPBES, 2022a), iii) the Thematic assessment of the sustainable use of wild species (IPBES, 2022b) and iv) the Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control (IPBES, 2024). Metrics retrieved from these assessments were aggregated (hereafter IPBES)
- The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is the United Nations' body to assess available scientific evidence related to climate change. The IPCC invites experts to assess the state of scientific, technical, and socio-economic knowledge on climate change, its impacts and future risks. Here, we focused on the Sixth Assessment Report, which consists of three Working Group contributions and a Synthesis Report. The Working Group I Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC, 2021) was reviewed here (hereafter IPCC), as it addresses the most up-to-date physical understanding of the climate system and climate change
- The Global Environmental Outlook (UN Environment, 2019) is a series of reports that review the state and direction of the global environment. It is a global process conducted by the United Nations Environment Programme at regional, national, and local levels around the world. The sixth edition of the Global Environment Outlook Healthy Planet, Healthy People (UN Environment, 2019) was included in this study (hereafter GEO)

The United Nations Information Portal on MEAs (<https://www.informeia.org/en>) identified 14 global treaties and protocols that focus on biological diversity. Information about how the agreements should be implemented and which indicators the signatory countries should report on is included in ancillary documentation, such as strategic plans and monitoring frameworks. 10

out of the 14 MEAs include either original or updated strategic plans and frameworks which were reviewed here:

- The Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) from the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (<https://www.cbd.int/gbf>). The monitoring framework of GBF is included in a package in CBD/COP/DEC/15/5 and the associated website (<https://www.gbf-indicators.org/>)
- The Sustainable Development Goals and targets of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDGs; <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/indicators-list/>). It includes a global indicator framework in A.RES.71.313 Annexe (<https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/indicators-list/>)
- The United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD; <https://www.unccd.int/>). It's updated Strategic Framework for 2018–2030 is published in ICCD/COP(13)/21/Add.1
- The Convention on Migratory Species (CMS; <https://www.cms.int/>). It developed a Strategic Plan for Migratory Species for 2015-2023.
- The Ramsar Convention on wetland conservation (<https://www.ramsar.org/>). Its 4th strategic plan for 2016 – 2024 is available (<https://www.ramsar.org/about/convention-wetlands-and-its-mission/strategic-plan/fourth-strategic-plan>)
- The Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES; <https://cites.org/eng/disc/what.php>). Its Strategic Vision for 2021-2030 is available (https://cites.org/eng/documents/Strategic_vision)
- The International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (<https://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/en/>). It includes the Strategic Plan For The Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (2023–2031)
- The Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (Water Convention; <https://unece.org/environment-policy/water>). It includes the Programme of Work of the Water Convention for 2022-2024
- The World Heritage Convention (WHC; <https://whc.unesco.org/en/convention/>). It includes a Strategic Action Plan for 2012 -2022. Updates to this document are currently under development
- The International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC, <https://www.ippc.int/en/>). It includes a Strategic Framework for 2020–2030

Data extraction

We employed two approaches to determine which indicators and other metrics were used in the listed assessments and MEAs: i) a **systematic search** of indicators and other metrics in the assessment reports, and ii) **direct extraction** of indicators proposed in documentation and convention texts from current MEAs.

Systematic search (assessment reports)

The systematic search was carried out using the keywords ‘indicator’, ‘index’, ‘indices’, and ‘indic’. The reports were loaded as PDFs in R using the pdftools package v3.3.3 (Ooms, 2016). All paragraphs with a match to these keywords were extracted along with the chapter and page numbers. Extracted paragraphs were analysed for appropriate metrics, and in cases where overarching concepts (e.g., climate change) were specified as indicators, measurable variables (e.g., changing temperatures, melting ice, etc.) were extracted instead. All appropriate metrics were extracted, documenting the paragraph, chapter, and page. Supplementary material and annexes to the different assessment reports were also included in the search; tables were scraped from the supplementary material of chapters 2 and 3 of the IPBES Global Assessment (Balvanera et al., 2019; Brauman et al., 2020; Purvis et al., 2019), chapter 2 of the IPBES Sustainable Use Assessment (Rice et al., 2022; Rice & Ticktin, 2022), and chapter 11 of the IPCC assessment.

Direct extraction (MEAS Strategic plans)

It was not necessary to systematically extract indicators from MEAs because they are listed in resolutions and annexes that accompany the main regulatory documents. Even though the Plant Treaty, UNESCO World Heritage Centre, International Plant Protection Convention, and the Water Convention include strategic plans, none of them identify specific indicators for party members to use in their reporting. Hence, these MEAs do not provide any indicators which could be used here.

Some of the indicators proposed in the MEAs are composed of multiple measurements (e.g. the indicators proposed for SDG 12.3.1: (a) food loss index and (b) food waste index). In these cases, we split the indicators according to the measurements suggested (e.g., food loss index and food waste index). Hence, the total number of indicators identified here might be higher than reported in the MEA documentation.

Data curation and classification

All extracted metrics were harmonised before combining them to avoid duplicated concepts. First, we removed non-English characters, trailing commas, and trailing spaces (*i.e.* space characters at the beginning or end of a metric name), and set metric names to lowercase. Next, we harmonised names that referred to the same metric but were phrased differently among sources (e.g., ‘Red List Index (species used for food and medicine)’ and ‘Red List Index (species used in food & medicine)’). The harmonisation process was automated and documented in open scripts that can be found in the IPBES-Data Organisation GitHub repository (<https://github.com/IPBES-Data/IPBES-Data-Indicators>).

Each harmonised metric was assigned to an element and sub-element of the social-ecological system it describes. The IPBES Conceptual framework (Díaz et al., 2015) defines six elements that constitute a social-ecological system: *Nature, Nature's contribution to people, Institutions, governance systems and other indirect drivers, Direct drivers of change, Good quality of life, and Anthropogenic assets*. We increased the granularity of the IPBES framework by disaggregating *Nature* into *Biodiversity* and *Ecosystem* components and *Anthropogenic assets* into *Human assets* and *Knowledge systems*. Hence, our framework has eight main elements: 1) *Biodiversity*, 2) *Ecosystems*, 3) *Ecosystem Services*, 4) *Direct Drivers of change*, 5) *Human well-being*, 6) *Governance*, 7) *Anthropogenic Assets*, 8) *Knowledge systems* (Table A1). These main elements were then subdivided based on more informative measurements (e.g., *Direct drivers of change* include the sub-elements *Climate change, Pollution, Land conversion, specific mention of Overexploitation or unsustainable use, Invasive alien species, (infectious) Diseases, and Natural drivers*) (Table A1).

Results

We retrieved 1829 unique metrics (indicators, variables, and indices): 657 from MEAs (Figure 1A) and 1356 from assessments (Figure 1B). Among MEAs, GBF and SDG have the most proposed metrics, followed by Ramsar, CITES, CMS, and UNCCD (Figure 1A, Table 1); among assessments, IPBES uses the most, followed by IPCC and GEO (Figure 1B, Table 2).

Figure 1: Counts of metrics (indicators, indices, variables) proposed in ongoing MEAs (A in graded blue) and assessment reports (B in graded green). The total number of metrics by source is above the bars.

Harmonisation considerably reduced duplicates in the dataset due to misspellings and punctuation issues. For instance, original indicator names listed in GBF were reduced from 333 to 311 (e.g., ‘Living Planet Index (for used species)’ and ‘Living Planet Index for used species’ were harmonised as ‘Living Planet Index (for used species)’). This process also facilitated the identification of metrics shared by multiple sources.

Indicators proposed in MEAs

Indicators proposed in MEAs include well-known or already developed indices (e.g., Red List Index, Species Habitat Index, Protected Connected Index), as well as metrics for which the methods are not always straightforward or developed (e.g., the indicator for GBF target 21 is described as: indicator on biodiversity information for monitoring the global biodiversity framework, outcome-based indicator(s) related to (extent of) wetland restoration possibly including remote sensing as appropriate). GBF and SDGs, with goals and targets covering a broad spectrum of topics, propose the largest number of indicators (Figure 1). CITES, CMS and Ramsar propose fewer and more targeted indicators measuring progress towards their specific goals and signatory parties (e.g., ‘number of CITES parties using the CITES checklist API’, ‘activity status/viability of CMS family of instruments’, ‘total hectares of Ramsar sites that have been designated’). They also include indicators targeting specific groups of species or regions (e.g., red list index (internationally traded species), red list index (migratory species), red list index (impacts of invasive alien species)). Hence, the reusability of indicators among MEAs is very low.

Table 1: Counts of unique indicators proposed in Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs).

*Values in parentheses indicate the total number of indicators proposed in each MEA.

Multilateral Environmental Agreement	Number of unique indicators proposed*
GBF	263 (311)
SDGs	192 (240)
RAMSAR	65 (65)
CITES	52 (52)
CMS	25 (25)
UNCCD	12 (13)

Metrics used in assessments

In contrast to MEAs, many of the metrics included in the reviewed assessments are variables or concepts that do not have a clear methodological development behind them (*e.g.*, ‘absence of conflict as indicator of political stability’, ‘cultural continuity’, ‘harvest intensity’, and ‘sustainable fishing practices’). Variables, indicators, and indices are used indistinctly within assessments, and they are not used to measure progress toward goals, but to measure or describe the status and trends of the different elements of the socio-ecological system.

The series of IPBES assessments included in this study provides the largest set of metrics (Figure 1B, Table 2) since it includes thematic and methodological assessments that cover particular aspects of nature and people.

Table 2: Counts of unique indicators, indices and variables used in each assessment. *Values in parentheses

Assessment report	Number of unique metrics*
IPBES	766 (797)
IPCC	369 (376)
GEO	185 (219)

indicate the number of total indicators used in each assessment report.

Re-use of metrics among MEAs and assessments

Only 11.4% of the metrics (209 out of 1829) are used in more than one assessment and/or MEA. Some common indicators among MEAs and assessments are: ‘Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies’ shared by GBF, SDG, UNCCD, and IPBES, and ‘Red List Index’, ‘Proportion of fish stocks within biologically sustainable levels’, ‘Index of coastal eutrophication potential (ICEP)’, ‘Forest area as a percentage of total land area’, ‘Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture’, ‘Level of water stress (freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources)’, ‘Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area’, and ‘Proportion of population using safely managed drinking water services’ used in GBF, SDG, IPBES, and GEO.

IPBES assessments share the largest number of metrics with SDGs (138) followed by GBF (80), GEO (29), IPCC (2), and UNCCD (1), whereas the IPCC assessment only shares metrics with other

assessments and does not include metrics used in any of the revised MEAs (Figures 2, 3). GEO assessment shares metrics with IPBES (29), GBF (22), SDGs (13), and IPCC (5; Figures 2, 3). IPBES and GEO assessments share 254 metrics with MEAs, representing 38.6% of the indicators proposed in MEAs. Regarding MEAs, 83.3 % of the indicators included in SDGs (200 out of 240) are also used in IPBES (138), GBF (48), GEO (13), and UNCCD (1); similarly, 48.6% of indicators included in GBF (151 out of 311) are also used in IPBES (80), SDGs (48), GEO (22), and UNCCD (1) (Figures 2, 3). UNCCD includes one indicator, which is also included in GBF, SDGs, and IPBES ('Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies'). Ramsar, CITES, and CMS propose their own indicators and do not use any of the indicators presented in assessments or other MEAs (Figures 2, 3).

Figure 2: Matrix showing counts of shared metrics among sources.

Figure 3: Metrics usage among sources (graded blue for MEAs and graded green for assessments). The width of the link represents the number of metrics.

The socio-ecological system being described

The extracted metrics cover all elements of the socio-ecological system (Figure 4). All metrics were assigned to at least one main element, with 22.4% (409 out of 1829) assigned to two. More than a quarter of the metrics describe the *Status and trends of Ecosystems* (28.3%), followed by *Governance* (14.2%), *Direct Drivers of change* (12.1%), *Knowledge Systems* (11.3%), *Biodiversity* (10.4%), *Human Assets* (9.2%), *Human Well-Being* (7.7%), and *Ecosystem Services* (6.7%) (Table A2).

All assessments include metrics that describe all elements of the socio-ecological system (Table A3). IPBES and GEO include a balanced distribution of indicators across all elements, whereas IPCC indicators are skewed towards *Ecosystems* and *Direct drivers* (Figure 4, Table A3). In contrast, MEAs typically focus on select elements of the socio-ecological system, with GBF and SDG being the exceptions that include indicators describing all elements (Figure 4, Table A3). GBF mostly proposes indicators on *Ecosystems*, *Governance*, and *Biodiversity*, whereas SDGs include indicators that mostly describe *Human assets*, *Governance*, and *Human Well-Being* (Figure 4, Table A3). Ramsar mostly includes indicators describing *Governance*, *Knowledge systems*, and *Ecosystems*; it does not include indicators on *Human Assets*. CMS focuses on *Biodiversity*,

Governance, and *Knowledge systems*. UNCCD mostly includes indicators on *Governance and Ecosystems*, whereas CITES mostly focuses on *Governance* (Figure 4, Table A3).

Our analysis of sub-element coverage identified that 15.6% of the metrics describe *Abiotic Conditions* (within *Ecosystems*) and are used mostly in IPCC; 7.3% describe the *State of Biodiversity* (within *Biodiversity*) and are used by IPBES, GEO, IPCC, GBF, CMS, and SDG; and 5.6% describe *Nature-Based Legislation* (within *Governance*) and are used by IPBES, GEO, GBF, SDG, CITES, RAMSAR, and CMS. Metrics developed by Indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLC), based on their Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK), were only used in IPBES assessments. Examples include 'totem or culturally important species', 'distance travelled to harvest resources' and prevalence of knowledge about seasonal cycles in their communities. By contrast, metrics describing or using information about IPLC were used by IPBES, GBF, CMS, CITES, and Ramsar. Examples of the latter include 'extent of indigenous peoples and local communities' lands that have some form of recognition', 'linguistic diversity index', and 'percentage of parties that co-developed or otherwise supported the capacity of indigenous peoples and local communities to pursue livelihoods'.

Figure 4: Attributions from different assessments and MEAs (left black bordered boxes) to elements of the socio-ecological system (right black bordered boxes). The width of the lines represents the number of metrics associated with each element.

Discussion

Our systematic review of 1,829 socio-ecological indicators and metrics proposed in biodiversity-focused Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs) and global environmental assessments revealed a highly heterogeneous landscape with surprisingly little overlap across frameworks. This outcome is expected to some degree, given the diversity of goals pursued by MEAs and science-policy assessments, and the inherent complexity of measuring socio-ecological systems. However, the low reusability of indicators—only 11.4% were shared between MEAs and assessments—may point out the lack of coordination between international policy processes and scientific assessments (i.e., assessments not considering the needs of MEAs and/or MEAs being poorly informed about existing indicators used in assessments). The Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) is a notable exception, reusing a relatively higher proportion of indicators from both MEAs and assessments (48.6%), suggesting that it may serve as a bridge between these communities.

Beyond low overlap, we identified a lack of consistency in indicator use, naming, and conceptualisation. In particular, the interchangeable use of “indicator,” “metric,” “variable,” and “index” in assessments and scientific literature in general blurs distinctions that are crucial for policy application. While general indicators are often favoured for their broad applicability, they may lack the spatial or temporal specificity required to evaluate progress meaningfully at local or national levels (Fraixedas et al., 2022; Jetz et al., 2019; Vicente et al., 2022). Conversely, many MEA indicators are highly specialised, limiting their relevance beyond their particular context. Together, this fragmentation complicates comparative analyses and creates additional reporting burdens for Parties, especially for developing economies with limited capacity. Some of the burdens are related to the cost and delays associated with gathering information, the steep learning and development curve of some metrics, which result in failures in the implementation of management and monitoring plans (Teixeira et al., 2016).

Our classification further revealed imbalances in the coverage of socio-ecological system elements. Indicators related to biodiversity and ecosystems are disproportionately represented, reflecting long-standing strengths in natural sciences. By contrast, aspects of human–nature relationships, Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK), and ecosystem services remain underrepresented, despite their centrality for linking ecological change with human well-being and economic systems. The lack of ecosystem service indicators is particularly notable, as they provide one of the few ways to translate ecological change into financial or capital terms. This imbalance likely reflects differences in research investment and capacity, as social–ecological and transdisciplinary approaches are still emerging and less institutionalised in global monitoring frameworks.

To address these challenges, we argue that all indicators used in the global policy arena should, at a minimum, adhere to Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR), and Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics (CARE; Carroll et al., 2020) principles. CARE principles, which are specifically relevant for ILK-related indicators, could even be taken beyond Indigenous data. For indicators to be FAIR and CAREful, the underlying data and protocols to calculate them should follow the same principles (Sica et al., 2024). FAIR and CAREfully collected data, well-documented protocols, and indicators supported by guidelines for reproducing each step will enhance the discoverability of indicators, their applicability and validity. Standardisation of metadata for data, protocols, and indicators would streamline data needs, avoid misleading interpretations, promote proper classification of indicators based on what they measure, and increase their reusability. Publicly accessible indicator repositories, coupled with transparent workflows and complete metadata, would prevent monopolisation of policy-relevant data, enable customisation for national or local contexts, and reduce inequities in reporting capacities. Such practices would also improve comparability across frameworks and strengthen accountability in tracking global progress towards environmental goals.

An important contribution of this study is the development of a harmonised catalogue of indicators used in biodiversity-focused MEAs and global assessments. This catalogue, which links each indicator to its original source and application, provides a valuable resource for identifying redundancies, gaps, and potential proxies. It also enables users to trace the scope and priorities of different frameworks and MEAs, thereby informing the design of new indicators and improving alignment between science and policy. While our classification schema offers a useful way to organise indicators, we acknowledge the subjectivity involved in assigning metrics to specific socio-ecological elements. Some indicators, such as land-use change or the Red List Index, capture multiple dimensions, and their interpretation may vary across contexts. By making all input data and harmonisation steps openly available, we enable transparent evaluation of these decisions and provide a basis for iterative refinement.

Our analysis was limited to biodiversity-focused MEAs listed under InforMEA, complemented by major science-policy assessments. Other international agreements, such as the Cartagena and Nagoya Protocols, or regional agreements (e.g., CCAMLR, UNECE Water Convention), were not included; future work could extend the analysis to these frameworks. In addition, the semi-automated extraction of indicators from assessments introduced challenges in distinguishing metrics, variables, and indicators, reflecting the underlying conceptual inconsistencies in the literature itself. Future methodological developments, including automated text-mining and sensitivity analyses, could improve reproducibility and comparability.

Conclusion

Overall, our findings demonstrate that the multiplicity of indicators is both necessary—reflecting the diversity of socio-ecological systems—and problematic, leading to inefficiencies, inconsistencies, and reporting burdens. By applying the FAIR and CARE principles, improving coordination between MEAs and science-policy assessments, and addressing gaps in socio-ecological coverage, the global community can move towards a more coherent and usable set of indicators. The harmonised catalogue presented here is a first step toward this goal, offering a transparent, comprehensive, and adaptable resource to guide indicator selection, comparison, and future development.

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